

DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article covers the essence of information and communication technologies and their importance in socio-economic life, the development of information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan and the practice of financing from the information and Communication Technology Development Fund.

Keywords: Communication, IT, e-government, education system, youth appeal platform.

Information technology in general is the technology of data management and processing. Usually under this term is understood computer technology. In the field of information technology, work is carried out on activities such as the collection, storage, Protection, processing, transmission of various information through electronic computing machines (Ehms) and computer networks. As the main technical means of Information Technology, Computing-in addition to organizational techniques, means of communication - telephone, teletype, telefax, etc. are used.

Although information technology has existed at various stages of human development, the peculiarity of the now informed society is that for the first time in the history of civilization, the effort spent on the achievement and production of knowledge is gaining priority over the expenditure on energy, raw materials, materials and material consumer items, that is, information technology occupies a leading place among existing new technologies. The industrial complex of Information Technologies is made up of a computer, a communication system, a database, a knowledge base and related fields of activity. In our country, work is underway to create an electronic platform “*youth appeal*”, which serves to establish direct communication between young people and those responsible. This platform serves to ensure that young people receive Science, become professional, in a word, find their place in life. Digital technology training centers will be opened in more than a hundred cities and districts in the current year in order to further interest the growing generation in the ICT sector, to improve their knowledge and skills in this regard. At the same time, in order to ensure the continuation of scientific research of young people in the field, to further expand, a branch of the University of Information Technology and technical schools in all regions will be established in the Tashkent region. It can be safely said that the project “one million programmers”, which is being implemented on the initiative of the head of state, is an important strategic step towards perspective. More than 120,000 students attended the project, of which more than 18,000 successfully completed the courses. In the next two years, the information systems “online, Digital, Secure specialized school”, “management of Higher Education processes” will be launched, which will bring this figure to 300 thousand and make them available for free training in the direction of computer technology, distance education and classes online. As of 2021, tasks have been set to cover up to 50% of the cost to young people who have won international it certificates. Consistent work is also being carried out to support IT startups and support entrepreneurs working in the ICT sector. In particular, IT Incubation Centers are being established under local higher education institutions. Nowadays, similar centers are located in

G.V. The branch of the Plekhanov Russian University of Economics in Tashkent, Tashkent Financial Institute, Tashkent State University of Economics, Inha, Amity, Turin Polytechnic universities, Institute of counter-engineering and economics, Andijan Institute of Mechanical Engineering, Andijan Institute of Agriculture and agrotechnologies in Tashkent.

On October 6, 2020, the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to further improve the educational system in the field of Information Technology, develop scientific research and integrate them with IT industry” was adopted. In accordance with it, in the previous year, specialized base schools were established and equipped, enterprises and organizations in the system were attached to them as sponsors, and more than 10 billion rubles were allocated. The resolution also provides for the establishment of 82 specialized schools in 2021, 64 in 2022, and 45 in 2023. Such measures indicate the scale of reforms that began in the field. Improving the comfort of the population and improving the efficiency of state bodies, improving e-government is one of the priority areas of digitization processes. The creation of an effective mechanism for interactive communication between state bodies and the population not only provides the basis for saving time and funds of citizens, but at the same time radically improving the functioning of state bodies, saving their time and costs through electronic document management, ensuring openness and transparency.

A single interactive public services portal plays an important role in the development of the e-government system (my.gov.uz). In 2020, significant work was carried out as part of the development of a single portal service. In particular, last year, 9.8 million applications were received through the portal. The number of users of the single portal increased to 185 thousand, reaching 380 thousand. Today, 218 public services are provided through the single portal. At the beginning of this year, a new service was introduced. Now citizens only interactive public services portal (my.gov.uz) can apply to exchange a biometric passport for an ID card.

Consistent work is underway to improve the unified interactive public services portal and create greater user comfort. In particular, a mobile application of the unified interactive public services portal running on the Android and OS platform was created and launched. The functional aspects of the program allow you to carry out a search through keywords, conduct process monitoring of the review of the submitted application, view the geolocation of public service centers. Another important advantage of the single portal is that citizens can use public services with a 10 percent discount, preferentially. In recent years, significant work has been done to improve the digital economy and the e-government system. In order to ensure their logical continuity, “roadmaps” are developed, the implementation of which is consistently ensured. Measures are being taken to eliminate the shortcomings and problems that are occurring immediately. In this regard, comprehensive measures were prescribed. In particular, according to the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy, 1,627 projects will be implemented in the next three years, with a total of more than 2.6 trillion soums for the digital transformation of Regions and networks. In particular, within the framework of the “Digital Tashkent” program, work is underway to create and integrate more than 30 information systems, implement the “Unified ambulance information system, and implement the “Electronic Polyclinic” information system in 88 multidisciplinary and family polyclinics in Tashkent.

In order to increase the role of the foundation for the development of information and communication technologies in the processes of implementation and use of information and

communication technologies in the sectors of the economy, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan said, Resolution No. 1836 of October 23, 2012" on the organization of activities of the state committee for informatization and telecommunications technologies "and resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on the further development of the information and Communication Technology Development Fund and the effective use of its funds "No. 356 of 19.12.2012" were adopted. The foundation for the development of information and communication technologies with these regulatory documents was established in order to provide funds for projects, research works of priority and social importance in the field of communication, informatization and development of information and communication technologies.

The following are sources of formation of funds:

- ❖ 50% of the proceeds from the payment of the state fee for the issuance of a license granting the right to carry out activities in the field of telecommunications;
- ❖ Until January 1, 2018, 20% of the proceeds from the payment for the use of the subscriber number;
- ❖ From January 1, 2018, 70% of the proceeds from the payment for the use of the subscriber number;
- ❖ 45% of funds levied as penalty from legal entities carrying out activities in the field of communication, regardless of requirements of regulatory legal acts in the field of communication, standards, forms of ownership for violation of the quality of services provided and departmental subordination, excluding economic penalties and fines imposed for violation of competition legislation;
- ❖ Income from the placement of temporary free funds of the fund in the form of bank deposits and other forms in accordance with current legislation;
- ❖ Charitable donations of legal entities and individuals, as well as international organizations.

The amount of income and expenses of the fund in 2020 amounted to 593,726.0 million. the sum was 4.5% in 2021, up from 620,290.0 mln. som. And in 2022, the amount of income and expenses of the fund amounted to 928,550.0 million. the sum was projected to be (150% compared to the previous year).

Funds can be issued only on the basis of relevant licenses to legal entities carrying out their activities on the territory of the Republic, regardless of forms of ownership, as well as educational, research institutions, regulatory, management bodies in the field of communication, informatization and telecommunication technologies, and organizations of this field for the implementation of interdepartmental integrated information systems of¹.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the goals in the field of Information Communication Technology are large. The main thing is to ensure their execution in good quality on time. Consequently, the ministry has set itself the goal of achieving great achievements for the development of the industry, fully employing its capabilities and potential in this regard.

¹ Kharatova, S. (2022, November). The role of integrated education in teaching foreign languages. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).

Information technology is considered an important-tool in ensuring the openness of the reform process, establishing an effective information exchange mechanism between the state and society. At the moment, the establishment of special virtual receptions of government, ministries and departments, as well as members of Parliament for effective communication with the population, serves, first of all, to continuously improve legislation in the field in harmony with world practice, to inform the general public of the content and essence of new laws and to effectively implement them into practice. This will especially help to communicate with the general public, to fulfill the urgent issue in the future and tasks in harmony with vital requirements and desires.

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